

IMPACT OF FISCAL POLICY ON UNEMPLOYMENT RATE IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *The study determined the extent fiscal policy affected unemployment rate in Nigeria. The study employed total government expenditure, total government revenue and total public debt as the independent variables. Data were extracted from Central bank Statistical Bulletin spanning from 2000 to 2023. The multiple regression analysis revealed that total government expenditure has a positive significant effect on unemployment rate in Nigeria. However, the table revealed that total government revenue and total public debt have negative significant effect on unemployment rate in Nigeria. Meanwhile fiscal policy is a veritable tool in addressing unemployment rate in Nigeria by directly influencing economic activity and job creation. This study therefore concluded that fiscal policy has a significant effect on unemployment rate in Nigeria. Based on the findings, the study recommended among others, that government of Nigeria needs to increase investments in specific industrial area; these investments are expected to increase the number of industries and create employment thereby reducing unemployment rate.*

Keywords: *Total government expenditure, Total government revenue, Total public debt and Unemployment rate.*

Introduction

Fiscal policy plays a crucial role addressing unemployment in Nigeria by directly influencing economic activity and job creation. For example, increased government spending on infrastructure projects such as road and construction not only improves transportation networks but also generates jobs for engineers, construction workers, and support staff. Similarly, tax incentives and reductions can stimulate private sector investment and expansion, leading to more job opportunities in industries ranging from manufacturing to services (Nwikina, Nwankwo & Thankgod, 2024). Social program like unemployment benefits provide essential support to individuals during job transitions, helping to maintain consumer spending levels and overall economic stability. Moreover, targeted labor market policies such as vocational training programs and job placement services help match unemployed individuals with available job openings, reducing the frictional unemployment rate.

The operational structure of both monetary and fiscal policies is essential for fine-tuning the progress of any economy across the globe. Broadly speaking, the purpose of any macroeconomic policy is to attain a high level of national income, ensure economic growth, achieve stable prices, maintain a healthy balance of payments, as well as engender full employment levels. It is impossible to overstate the role played by the interaction of fiscal and monetary policy in coordinating economic policies in a developing economy like Nigeria to address the problems posed by various economic fluctuations like poverty, inflation, unemployment and inequality (Adenaike, 2022).

Over the years, the importance of monetary policy in influencing macroeconomic factors such as unemployment has become more prominent. Economic postulations before the 1930s, commonly referred to as classical economics were dominated by the opinion that money has no effect on the real variables of the economy. Hence, money is not significant, according to the classical school (Olurinola & Egbe, 2024). The Keynesians on the other hand, debunked this view and argued vehemently that money has an effect on the real sector of the economy operating through interest rates. The rise of this school of thought gave impetus to the formulation of fiscal policies. Fiscal policy as a tool of macroeconomic policies also plays an essential role in the reduction of unemployment in an economy. Both monetary and fiscal policies play a key role in the promotion of the main government objective of promoting the citizens' welfare (Ogah et al. 2021).

Unemployment in Nigeria remains a persistent challenge, affecting millions of lives and posing significant hurdles to economic prosperity. Unemployment refers to individuals who are willing and able to work but are unable to find employment. According to Musa et al (2021) unemployment refers to the percentage of the labour force that is without a job but is able and willing to work at the prevailing wage rate. In line with this view, Oloruntuyi (2021) described unemployment as the number of people who do not have a job, have actively searched for work within the past four weeks and are currently available for employment. In Nigeria, unemployment rates have been a significant economic challenge. As of 2023, the unemployment rate stood at 33% with youth unemployment at 45%, according to data from the Nigerian National Bureau of Statistics. This is an indication of high and rising unemployment rate. High unemployment rates in Nigeria have several implications.

Many studies have tried to examine the impact of either monetary or fiscal policy on unemployment in Nigeria. However, this study would focus on the introduction of interactive terms which capture the effects which using both policies would have on the rate of unemployment in the Nigerian economy. In addition to that, this study uses Auto-regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL). The study adds to the body of knowledge by focusing on these identified gaps stated.

This study assesses the impact of fiscal policy on unemployment rate in Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the effect of government expenditure on unemployment rate in Nigeria.

2. Ascertain the effect of government revenue on unemployment rate in Nigeria.

3. Examine the effect of public debt on unemployment rate in Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Fiscal policy is important in stimulating and stabilizing a depressed economy since it plays a substantial role in resource utilization, poverty reduction, and inflation management, among other things. According to Anyafor (2016), fiscal policy is one component of government policy concerned with the use of taxation, public expenditure, and other financial programs included in the annual budget and deciding how best to use the gathered revenue to achieve national goals. The goal of modern fiscal policy is to increase economic efficiency and stability. Adigwe, Echekoba, and Justus (2015) opined that monetary policy is a major economic stabilization tool that serves as measures to regulate and control the volume, cost, availability, and direction of money and credit in an economy to achieve certain macroeconomic goals. In Nigeria, the Central Bank uses the monetary policy rate (MPR) which signifies the direction of interest rates as a nominal anchor, to conduct monetary policy. In any economy, monetary policy has the crucial function of regulating the money supply by targeting inflation or reaching full employment.

Unemployment Rate

The unemployment rate measures the percentage of the working-age population who are unemployed but looking for work. The labour force consists of both employed and idle individuals. The unemployment rate accurately depicts the extent to which persons who are ready to work are able to find and actively work (Olurinola & Egbe, 2024). Unemployed people are those who are currently out of work but are willing and capable to work and have actively searched for work. Currently, the unemployment rate is estimated to be 33.3 percent, which is projected to rise in 2022 (NBS, 2021). It is projected to rise further in 2022. Unemployment is regarded as the root of poverty in Nigeria according to (Akinmulegun, 2014). According to the Keynesian Theory, unemployment is as a result of a reduction in government spending in an economy and that significant government intervention is required to meet employment and output targets. Keynesian unemployment is caused by downturns in the economy that are part of the business cycle, which are the natural fluctuations in the economy (Amu, Osabuohien & Alege, 2021).

Empirical Review

Nwikina, Nwankwo and Thankgod (2024) examined fiscal policy response to unemployment in Nigeria from 1991 to 2022. Data were obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria. Domestic debt, external debt, capital expenditure, recurrent expenditure, oil revenue, and tax revenue are adapted to proxy fiscal policy while unemployment is used as the dependent variable. The analyzed model's result using the bound test established that there is no long-run relationship between fiscal policy and

unemployment. Osho-Itsueli, Egbon and Obi (2024) determined the impact of public finance operations on unemployment rate in West African Monetary Zone (WAMZ) Countries. The study employed Pooled Mean Group/ Autoregressive Distributed Lag technique to achieve this objective. Data on public expenditure, public revenue and public debt were the independent variables and unemployment rate as the dependent variable were gathered and used for the estimation analysis. The findings revealed a positive effect of public finance operations on unemployment rate but the effect was found to be statistically insignificant. Akindele, Oloba and Mah, (2023) evaluated the drivers of unemployment intensity in the sub-Saharan region adopting the Pooled Mean Group (PMG) estimator and the utilized stochastic frontier to generate government efficiency index from 1991 to 2017. The study revealed that the endowments of national resources had a significant and positive relationship with employment generation. Celikay (2023) studied the impact of social spending on chronic unemployment in some selected countries within the organization for economic co-operation and development countries. Auto-regressive distributed lag approach and the error correction model were employed by the study. The result indicated was that variations in the share of social expenditures in GDP within the selected countries affect unemployment in the same rate. Okoye and Obi (2022) analyzed the nexus between public debts, poverty and unemployment in Nigeria; With secondary data on internal and external public debts, poverty and unemployment rate collected from the Central Bank of Nigeria Bulletin and the National Bureau of Statistics and the use of unrestricted vector auto-regression model, the study showed that public debts had no significant impact on poverty but public debts were discovered to influence the level of unemployment rates in Nigeria. George-Anokwuru (2022) ascertained the effect of fiscal policy on employment generation in Nigeria spanning from 1981 to 2020. Data were extracted from the statistical bulletin of Nigerian central bank and Bureau of Statistics. The Error Correction Model was applied as the main analytical tool. The study revealed that aggregate government expenditure has a positive but insignificant influence on the employment rate. In addition, total tax revenue and external debt service have negative and insignificant influences on the employment rate in Nigeria. Ejemezu, Agu and Ude (2021) examined the impact of fiscal policy instrument on unemployment in Nigeria using time series annual data from 1990- 2020 which constitutes 30 years observations. Data obtained from the CBN annual statistical bulletin. The data were analyzed using ADF unit root test, co-integration test and ARDL Model. The study found that Government Borrowing has a positive and no significant effect on Unemployment in Nigeria. Taxation has a positive and no significant impact on Unemployment in Nigeria, Government Expenditure has a positive and no significant impact on Unemployment in Nigeria.

Shuaibu, Muhammad, Abdullahi and Gwazawa (2021) studied the impact of public debt on inflation and unemployment in Nigeria. The auto-regressive distributed lag approach and the error correction

model was used on data collected from 1985-2020. The study indicated that there is a long run association between public debt and unemployment rate in Nigeria. Obisike, Okoli, Onwuka and Mba (2020) examined the effect of government social expenditure on unemployment in Nigeria. Ordinary Least Square regression method was employed to test the data. The study revealed that government expenditure (both recurrent and capital) on health; education and other social activities do not contribute to unemployment reduction which does not conform to a-priori expectations. Olukayode, and Olorunfemi (2018) evaluated the effect of fiscal policy instruments on employment generation in Nigeria within the periods of 1980-2015. The study employed the Augmented Dickey Fuller test to estimate the stationarity level, Engel Granger cointegration test for long-run relationship and ordinary least square for long-run estimates. The study indicated that government spending and manufacturing output had negative impact on unemployment rate in Nigeria. Dikeogu and Karma (2018) determined the influence of fiscal policy on macroeconomic performance in Nigeria from 1970 to 2017. Data were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin. The study adopted the ARDL, Engle-Granger Co-integration and Error Correction Modelling techniques for the analysis. Data for the empirical analysis were sourced from secondary sources like CBN Statistical Bulletin. The study showed that a long run relationship exists between fiscal policy and macroeconomic performance.

Methodology

The study was adopted the *Ex Post Facto* research design and time series data. This design was adopted because the main aim of the study was to analysis the cause-effect relationship that exists between the dependent and the independent variable using the data that already existed and the study made no attempt to change it nature and values.

Data were generated from the International Monetary Fund, and central bank of Nigerian Statistical Bulletin in Nigeria. The data extracted were; money supply, exchange rate and inflation rate as the independent variables and per capital income represents dependent variable. The time series data covers twenty four (24) years from 2000 to 2023.

Model Specification

The multiple regression analysis helps analyze and understand the long term relationship between variables by considering the time lag and the past condition of the dependent and independent variables.

Thus, in order to ascertain the effect of money supply, exchange rate and inflation rate of the on per capital income, this study modified the econometric model of Ogini (2022) as specified thus;

$$PCI = f(M_2, EXR, ITR, IFR, UPR)$$

The Econometric Equation Form of the Model is:

$$PCI = \beta_0 + \beta_1 M_2 + \beta_2 EXR + \beta_3 ITR + \beta_4 IFR + \beta_5 UPR + \mu - \dots - i$$

Where:

PCI = Per Capita Income

M2= Broad Money Supply

EXR= Exchange Rate

ITR = Interest Rate.

IFR = Inflation Rate

UPR=Unemployment Rate

The modified model is specified thus:

$$UER = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TTE_{it} + \beta_2 TTR_{it} + \beta_3 DEBT_{it} + \mu \text{-----} -ii$$

Where:

UER = unemployment rate

TTE= total government expenditure

TTR= total government revenue

DEBT = Total public debt

μ = Stochastic Disturbance (Error Term)

β_0 = Intercept of Relationship in the Model Constant

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$, = The Coefficients of the Independent Variables

ϵ_{it} = Error term

i = Firm

t = Time (year)

Method of Data Analysis

The data were analysed comparatively via both descriptive and inferential analyse. The descriptive statistics was first conducted in order to gain understanding of the sample characteristics as regards the selected variables. Inferential statistical analysis was carried out with the aid of E-Views 9.0 statistical software. These include the following:

Coefficient of Correlation: which is a good measure of relationship between two variables, tells us about the strength of relationship and the direction of relationship as well;

Multiple Regression analysis: was used to predict the value of a variable based on the value of the other variables;

Decision Rule

The decision for the hypotheses is to accept the alternative hypotheses if the p-value of the test statistic is less than or equal to alpha and to reject the alternative hypotheses if the p-value of the test statistic is greater than alpha at 5% significance level.

Data analysis and Results

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	UER	TTE	TTR	DEBT
Mean	0.040896	5460.103	5594.172	11422.34
Median	0.037850	4204.958	5785.096	3136.837
Maximum	0.057400	19500.00	10435.06	97340.00
Minimum	0.030700	701.0509	1402.874	438.8909
Std. Dev.	0.006626	4960.249	2584.126	21925.78
Skewness	1.175656	1.525116	-0.096820	2.785249
Kurtosis	3.316918	4.491324	1.954271	10.48511
Jarque-Bera	22.51640	46.11186	4.524185	348.2294
Probability	0.000013	0.000000	0.104132	0.000000
Sum	3.926000	524169.9	537040.5	1096545.
Sum Sq.				
Dev.	0.004171	2.34E+09	6.34E+08	4.57E+10
Observations	96	96	96	96

Source: E-View output, 2025

The above table of descriptive analysis revealed that the unemployment rate (UER) is 0.041; the maximum value was 0.057 and a minimum value of 0.031, while standard deviation was 0.007. The mean average of total expenditure (TTE) shows 5460.10 with standard deviation of 4960.25; with maximum value of 19500.00 and a minimum value of 701.05. The mean value of total revenue (TTR) was 5594.17, a standard deviation value of 2584.13; maximum value of 10435.06 with a minimum value of 1402.87. The mean value of total debt (DEBT) was 11422.34, standard deviation of 21925.78; and maximum value of 97340.00 and a minimum value of 438.89. The Skewness is the measure of how much the probability distribution of a random variable changes from the normal distribution. Table 1 outlines that the probability distribution for UER (0.000); TTE (0.000); TTR (0.104) and BEDT (0.000) are positively skewed distribution.

Table 2: Pearson Correlation Matrix

	UER	TTE	TTR	DEBT
UER	1			
TTE	0.27249	1		
TTR	0.16489	0.76552	1	
DEBT	0.02728	0.89410	0.52497	1

Source: E-Views 9.0 Correlation Output, 2025

The table above revealed the Pearson Correlation Matrix relationship between independent and dependent variables. The result showed that TTE, TTR and DEBT have a positive correlation (0.272, 0.165 and 0.027) with unemployment rate in Nigeria.

Test of Hypotheses

Table 3: Multiple Regression analysis testing the effect between UER, TTE, TTR and DEBT

Dependent Variable: UER

Method: Panel Least Squares

Date: 07/24/25 Time: 23:24

Sample: 2000 2023

Periods included: 24

Cross-sections included: 4

Total panel (balanced) observations: 96

Variable	Coefficien t	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.040345	0.001277	31.60503	0.0000
TTE	3.13E-06	3.60E-07	8.712869	0.0000
TTR	-1.93E-06	3.63E-07	-5.301881	0.0000
DEBT	-5.06E-07	6.15E-08	-8.233515	0.0000
R-squared	0.469656	Mean dependent var	0.04089	6
Adjusted squared	R-0.452362	S.D. dependent var	0.00662	6
S.E. of regression	0.004903	Akaike info criterion	7.75708	2
Sum squared resid	0.002212	Schwarz criterion	7.65023	4
Log likelihood	376.3399	Hannan-Quinn criter.	7.713892	1.76002
F-statistic	27.15740	Durbin-Watson stat	4	0.00000
Prob(F-statistic)	0			

In Table 3 above, R-squared and adjusted Squared values were (0.47) and (0.45) respectively. This indicates that the independent variables explain about 45% of the systematic variations in unemployment rate over the twenty four years periods (2000-2023). The adjusted R^2 , which represents the coefficient of determinations suggest that 45% of the total variations in the dependent variable, unemployment rate is mutually explained by the independent variables (TTE, TTR and DEBT). The F- statistics value of 27.157 with an associated $\text{Prob.}>F = 0.000$ indicating that the model is fit to explain the association expressed in the study model and further advocates that the independent variables are properly selected, combined and used. The value of adjusted R^2 of 45% also revealed that 55% of the changes in the dependent variable are explained by other factors not captured in the study model.

Test of Autocorrelation: using Durbin-Waston (DW) statistics which we obtained from our regression result in table 3, it is observed that DW statistics is 1.760 and an Akika Info Criterion and Schwarz Criterion which are 7.757 and 7.650 respectively also further confirms that our model is well specified.

Hypothesis One

H_{01} : Total government expenditure has no significant effect on unemployment rate in Nigeria.

The table revealed that total government expenditure has a positive significant effect on unemployment rate in Nigeria. This can be observed from the beta coefficient (β_1) of 3.130 with t-statistic of 8.712. Since the P-value of the test was 0.000 less than 0.05 (5%), the study reject null hypothesis and upholds alternative hypothesis showing that total government expenditure has significant effect on unemployment rate in Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two

H_{02} : Total government revenue has no significant effect on unemployment rate in Nigeria.

The table revealed that total government revenue has a negative significant effect on unemployment rate in Nigeria. This can be observed from the beta coefficient (β_1) of -1.930 with t-statistic of -5.302. Since the P-value of the test was 0.000 less than 0.05 (5%), the study reject null hypothesis and upholds alternative hypothesis showing that total government revenue has significant effect on unemployment rate in Nigeria.

Hypothesis Three

H_{03} : Total public debt has no significant effect on unemployment rate in Nigeria.

The table revealed that total public debt has a negative significant effect on unemployment rate in Nigeria. This can be detected from the beta coefficient (β_1) of -5.060 with t-statistic of -8.234. Since the P-value of the test was 0.000 less than 0.05 (5%), the study reject null hypothesis and upholds

alternative hypothesis showing that this study upholds that total public debt has significant effect on unemployment rate in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The multiple regression analysis revealed that total government expenditure has a positive significant effect on unemployment rate in Nigeria. This can be observed from the beta coefficient (β_1) of 3.130 with t-statistic of 8.712. However, the table revealed that total government revenue and total public debt have negative significant effect on unemployment rate in Nigeria. This can be observed from the beta coefficient (β_1) of -1.930 with t-statistic of -5.302. Since the P-value of the test was 0.000 less than 0.05 (5%), and beta coefficient (β_1) of -5.060 with t-statistic of -8.234. Since the P-value of the test was 0.000 less than 0.05 (5%).

These results opposed the findings of Nwikina, Nwankwo, and Thankgod (2024) who revealed that domestic debt, capital expenditure and tax revenue had a negative but significant influence on unemployment. However, the external debt and recurrent expenditure reported an insignificant impact on unemployment rate. Osho-Itsueli, Egbon and Obi (2024) revealed a positive effect of public finance operations on unemployment rate but the effect was found to be statistically non-significant. George-Anokwuru (2022) showed that aggregate government expenditure has a positive but insignificant influence on the employment rate. In addition, total tax revenue and external debt service have negative and insignificant influences on the employment rate in Nigeria.

However, the results were confirmed by the findings of Okoye and Obi (2022) who reported that public debts have significant influence the level of unemployment rates in Nigeria. Shuaibu, Muhammad, Abdullahi and Gwazawa (2021) showed that there is a long run relationship between public debt and unemployment rate. The results further showed that public debt increase in Nigeria causes increases in unemployment although the external public debt was shown to have more effects on unemployment than the domestic debt.

Conclusion

The study determined the extent fiscal policy affected unemployment rate in Nigeria. The study employed total government expenditure, total government revenue and total public debt as the independent variables. Data were extracted from Central bank Statistical Bulletin spanning from 2000 to 2023. The multiple regression analysis revealed that total government expenditure has a positive significant effect on unemployment rate in Nigeria. However, the table revealed that total government revenue and total public debt have negative significant effect on unemployment rate in Nigeria. Meanwhile fiscal policy is a veritable tool in addressing unemployment rate in Nigeria by directly influencing economic activity and job creation. This study therefore concluded that fiscal policy has a significant effect on unemployment rate in Nigeria.

Based on the findings, the study recommended the following;

1. The government of Nigeria needs to increase investments in specific industrial area; these investments are expected to increase the number of industries and create employment thereby reducing unemployment rate.
2. The study recommended that government income such like tax revenue and agricultural output should be part of employment direct impact on unemployment rate in Nigeria.
3. Public borrowings need to be directed to specific productive sectors that will improve economic development demonstrated in terms of job creations.

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